

Speculation on Antiparticles from Special Relativity Part II

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In Part I, we suggested that the notion of antiparticles already exists in the Lorentz invariant $E^2 = p^2 + m^2$ ($c=1$) because one may have $|m|$ and $-|m|$ or $+E$. We argued that if m could become 0, one could still have an E^2 which cancels with p^2 , i.e. a photon solution. This argument, however, seems to be missing intermediate steps.

Here we start by assuming that one may have t and $-t$ because there is x and $-x$ if space-time really holds, i.e. if t and x may really be treated equally. Given that (x,t) forms a 4-vector as does $(0,m)$ and (p,E) , then one should also have the possibility to have $-|m|$ and $-|E|$. We then consider the sum of free particle actions, $-Et+px$ for a particle with $-|E|$ and t moving with $-p$ together with a usual particle with E,p , so the two come towards each other. Alternatively, one may use $|m|$ and $-|m|$ next to each other. Then $-(-E)t+px$ for this antiparticle plus $-Et+px$ for a usual particle equals 0. This, however, is equivalent to $-Et+px$ for two photons because $-Et+px=0$ for any photon. This allows one to conserve energy and momentum, thus there must be two photons. For the $-|E|$ case, one may consider this as $|E|$ with $-t$ (moving backwards in time and noted by Feynman) and so both photons have energy $|E|$.

Antiparticle

The notion of the antiparticle arose when Dirac linearized the Klein-Gordon equation which is based on:

$$E^2 = p^2 + m^2 \quad (c=1) \quad ((1))$$

By starting with a quadratic equation, he was able to consider $|m|$ and $-|m|$ as well as E and $-E$ as solutions of the linearized equation. In special relativity, however, one may start with a rest mass (at rest) in a frame and transform to (p,E) or $(-p,E)$ using a Lorentz transformation depending on whether a second frame moves with constant v or $-v$. As a result, p and $-p$ are associated with motion in one direction or the other. Physically, time is considered to move in the positive direction from 0. If one really has t and x on the same footing, however, one should not have this restriction on t . Mathematically, one could have $-t$. (x,t) form a 4-vector and so these arguments would also need to apply to E and m being either positive or negative. The quadratic equation ((1)) handles both positive and negative E and m values. A physical interpretation, however, would be needed for a $-|m|$ and a $-E$ for a free particle.

X and t on the Same Footing

As noted above, if x and t are on the same footing, one may have x and $-x$ and so should have t and $-t$. Physically, however, t is assumed to start at 0 and increase in the positive direction and so such a negative t is unusual.

Given that (p, E) or $(0, m_0 c^2)$ is also a 4-vector, this should imply that $-|E|$ and $-|m_0|$ are also possibilities. As a result, one may work with $-|E|$ or $-|m_0|$ with positive x and t in the Lorentz invariant:

$$A = -Et + px \quad ((2))$$

We consider the case of either $|m_0|$ and $-|m_0|$ or $-|E|$ with $-p$ and $|E|$ with p so that the two particles come towards each other. In either case, using positive x and t one has:

$$A(-|E|) + A(|E|) = 0 \quad ((3))$$

It is known, however, that $A=0$ for a photon in all cases. Thus, ((3)) may be considered equivalent to the sum of two photon A (actions or Lorentz invariants) such that momentum is conserved. The energy of each photon should then be considered equivalent to $|E|$ because the $-|E|$ case may be considered to be equivalent to a $|E|$ moving backwards in time.

Note: Feynman suggested that an antiparticle moves backwards in time (1).

Thus, it seems that one may use the notion of the action, i.e. the Lorentz invariant $-Et + px$, to provide a missing intermediate step in Part I.

We note that adding actions for the same x, t is the same as adding $(p_1 c, E_1)$ and $(p_2 c, E_2)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that if space-time x and t are on the same footing, one should be able to have $-t$ or t . It is, however, not clear what $-t$ means. Given that $(0, m_0 c^2)$ and (pc, E) are also 4-vectors, this seems to also imply that one may have $-|m_0|$ and $-|E|$. We consider the case of a $-|m_0|$ with a positive t and a $|m_0|$ with a positive t or a $-|E|$ with a $-p$ and an $|E|$ with a p (both with positive x and t) so that the particles come towards each other.

If one adds the action (Lorentz invariant: $-Et + px$) for this case, one obtains 0. The action of a photon, $-Et + px$, however, is 0 so one may consider this sum of A 's equivalent to the sum of the action of two photons. Two photons are needed to ensure conservation of momentum. One photon has energy $|E|$ equivalent to the particle with $|E|$. For the $-|E|$ particle, one may consider it to have $|E|$ and $-t$ (i.e. travel backwards in time), so for energy conservation the second photon must also have energy $|E|$. One may also apply this to $|m_0|$ and $-|m_0|$ so there is no particle-antiparticle momentum and the scenario is simpler. In this case, $-|m_0|$ with positive t is $|m_0|$ with $-t$, i.e. traveling backwards in time.

References

1. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Antiparticle>

